

ROMANIAN ACADEMIES

Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre
for Mountain Economy

Academy of Romanian Scientists / CCFRASMIA Oradea

Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences

Academy of National Security Sciences

Academy of Technical Sciences

TECHNICAL ORGANIZER

Association for Conscience and Freedom

IN COLLABORATION WITH

The Institute for Peace Studies in Eastern Christianity (Harvard Divinity
School) – United States of America

National Defense University Carol I – Romania

The "Bogdan Petriceicu Haşdeu" Institute of Romanian Philology of the
Ministry of Education, Culture and Research – Republic of Moldova

"1 December 1918" University of Alba Iulia – Romania

2nd International Workshop
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND
ACADEMIC ETHICS

November 5th, 2020

Online - <https://harvard.zoom.us>

The Workshop is associated with the International Conference
"Integrity and Freedom of Conscience", November 5th & 19th

In 2020 the conference and the workshop will be online

<https://harvard.zoom.us>

Scientific Committee

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Marian Simion. *Harvard Divinity School & The Institute for Peace Studies in Eastern Christianity – United States of America*

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Marius George Țical. *The Academy of National Security Sciences – Romania*

Otilia Manta. *Romanian Academy / "Victor Slavescu" Center for Financial and Monetary Research & Centre for Mountain Economy, & School of International University Studies / Instituto di Ricerca di Dr. Arioli S.a.s. – Italy & Vice-President of the European Union Experts (EUExperts) – Belgium*

Daive Barbieri. *Oxford University (Fellow) – United Kingdom & Link Campus University Intelligence – Italy*

Gabriel Xiao-Guang Yue. *Rattanakosin International College of Creative Entrepreneurship / Rajamangala University of Technology Rattanakosin – Thailand & Siksha 'O' Anusandhan University – India*

Andrian Vladimirov Aleksandrov. *Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" – Bulgaria*

Tamara Peicu. *University of Vienna – Austria*

David Harms. *Friedensau Adventist University (Fellow) – Germany & Andrews University – United States of America*

Artur Boldt. *Bogenhofen Seminary (Fellow) – Austria & Andrews University – United States of America*

Organizing Committee

Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru. *"Timotheus' Brethren Theological Institute of Bucharest & "Aurel Vlaicu" University of Arad – Romania*

Dragoş Muşat. *Association for Conscience and Freedom – Romania*

Denise E. Burrill. *Fitchburg State University – United States of America*

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Mihai Covaci. *Hyperion University – Romania & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria*

Nina Corcinschi. *The "Bogdan Petriceicu Haşdeu" Institute of Romanian Philology of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Research – Republic of Moldova*

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Carmen Cătună. *Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy*

Consuela Wagner. *Institut für Bildung und Persönlichkeitsförderung – Germany*

Ioana Borza. *Academy of Romanian Scientists – CCFRASMA Oradea & University of Oradea – Romania*

Marilena Marin. *"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania*

Corneliu Constantineanu. *"Aurel Vlaicu" University of Arad – Romania*

Mădălina Botină. *"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania*

Răzvan Anichitei. *Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy*

Welcome Speeches (EET, UTC/GMT+3h: 10.00 – 10.10; USA EDT, UTC/GMT-4h: 03.00-03.10)

Marian Simion. *Harvard Divinity School & The Institute for Peace Studies in Eastern Christianity – United States of America*

Dragoş Muşat. *Association for Conscience and Freedom*

Brînduşa Covaci. *Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria*

Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru. *‘Timotheus’ Brethren Theological Institute of Bucharest – Romania*

Keynote Speeches (EET, UTC/GMT+3h: 10.10 – 11.10; USA EDT, UTC/GMT-4h: 03.10-04.10)

Marian Gh. Simion. *Harvard Divinity School & The Institute for Peace Studies in Eastern Christianity – United States of America*

Paper: *Delusive Academic Ethics: Teaching for Capitalism, not for Civilization*

Şerban Turcuş. *“Babes-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca – Romania*

Paper: *Ethical Issues regarding the HIRSCH Index*

Florin Munteanu. *Academy of Romanian Scientists & Academy of Technical Sciences*

Paper: *From Complicated to Complex, a New Scientific Approach of Gaia Model*

Mihai Himcinschi. *“1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia – Romania*

Paper: *Deontology, Competence and Academic Integrity*

Emil Jurcan. *“1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia – Romania*

Paper: *Academic Deontology from a Theological Perspective*

Break (EET, UTC/GMT+3h: 11.10 – 11.15; USA EDT, UTC/GMT-4h: 04.10-04.15)

Section I – Society and Technical Science, Scientific Research and Academic Ethics (EET, UTC/GMT+3h: 11.15 – 13.25; USA EDT, UTC/GMT-4h: 04.15-06.25)

*Chair: **Brindusa Covaci.** Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria*

*Discussants: **Radu Rey.** Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy*

***Viorel Buta.** Academy of National Security Sciences – Romania*

***Alina Livia Nicu.** University of Craiova – Romania*

***Adi Mustață.** National University Defence Carol I – Romania*

***Adrian Turek Rahoveanu.** University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest – Romania*

"Mountain product", food - medicine to prevent / combat the phenomena generated by the COVID-19 pandemic	Radu Rey. Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy
Innovative Approach regarding Realities and Perspectives of the Romanian Research in the Defense Science in the New European Context	Viorel Buta, Mihail Anton. Academy of National Security Sciences & National University Defence Carol I – Romania
The Justice and Higher Legal Education in the Era of Forced Digitalization	Cristian Dumitru Miheș. University of Oradea – Romania
Considerations regarding the Appreciation of the Originality of Scientific Works in the Legal Sciences	Alina Livia Nicu. University of Craiova – Romania
Scientific Research regarding the New Dynamic of Mountain Science	Brindusa Covaci. Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria
Current Challenges of Scientific Research in the Criminological area	George-Mircea Botescu. University of Bucharest – Romania

Data Revolution: Ethical Creativity in Scientific Research	Denise E. Burrill. <i>Fitchburg State University – United States of America</i>
Methodological and Ethical Challenges of Research in the Field of Military Sciences	Adi Mustață, Alexandru Lucinescu, Ruxandra Buluc, Cosmin Buta. <i>National University Defence Carol I – Romania</i>
Social Prerequisites for Successful Ethical Education	Consuela Wagner. <i>Institut für Bildung und Persönlichkeitsförderung – Germany</i>
Scientific Research and Academic Ethics reflected in the Graduation Papers. Legal Field	Marilena Marin. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Scientific Researches regarding Pădurea Craiului Mountains	Radu Brejea. <i>Academy of Romanian Scientists – CCFRASMIA Oradea – & University of Oradea – Romania</i>
Ethical Values, Permanent Source of Determination and Motivation for Academic Results	Otilia Manta. <i>School of International University Studies / Istituto di Ricerca di Dr. Arioli S.a.s. – Italy & Vice-President of the European Union Experts (EUExperts) – Belgium</i>
Digital Ethics and Higher Education	Mădălina Botină. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Academic Research between Honesty and Pragmatism	Laurențiu Tănase. <i>Bucharest University & Romanian Academy - Institute for the Research of Quality of Life – Romania</i>
Paradigmatic and Conceptual Changes in Scientific Research and Academic Ethics	Delia Mariana Ardelean. <i>"Vasile Goldis" University of Arad – Romania</i>
Phd in Romania Today: Challenges and Perspectives	Gheorghe Negustor. <i>"Babes-Bolyai" University, Cluj-Napoca – Romania</i>
Scientific and Ethical Methods and Techniques Addressed in Advising Pupils and Students	Liana Rozalia Rotaru. <i>The County Center of Resources and Educational Assistance – Romania</i>

New Challenges regarding Scientific Research in Agronomy	Ioana Borza. <i>Academy of Romanian Scientists – CCFRASMIA Oradea- Romania</i>
Academics Ethics in Bulgaria: Cultural Challenges and State Policy	Andrian Vladimirov Aleksandrov. <i>Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" – Bulgaria</i>
Religious Conscience and the Premises of Academic Integrity	Adrian Neagu. <i>SDA Adventist Church, Romanian Union – Romania</i>
Effects of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on the Scientific Research in Romania	Nicoleta Mihaila. <i>Romanian Academy / "Victor Slavescu" Center for Financial and Monetary Research – Romania</i>
Scientific Observation. Qualitative Field Research and Ethical Principles of Scientific Research	Gheorghe Radu. <i>Athenaeum University – Romania</i>
Research Methods used in Studies regarding Agricole Exploitation	Adrian Turek Rahoveanu. <i>University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest – Romania</i>
Scientific Research in the Context of Alternative University Education (Public and Private) – Provocations and Reconsiderations	Dumitru Nica. <i>The National Defense University Carol I – Romania</i>
Ethics and Academic Integrity in online Education. Teaching strategies for “distant learning” or “low-frequency” Education	Veronica Cristina Nedelcu. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Academic Activism and Ethical Neutrality in Scientific Research	Tamara Abigail Peicu. <i>University of Vienna – Austria</i>
Academic Ethics Regarding Teacher Training	Vasile Drăghici. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Approaches regarding Religion in the 21 st Century and the Academic Ethics	Tutu Pisleag. <i>Academy of National Security Sciences – Romania</i>
The Importance of Continuous Scientific Research of Teachers	Mariana Mitra-Niță. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Respecting the Principles of Bioethics in the Case of Vulnerable Populations in the Context of	Cristina-Luiza Erimia. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>

Multicenter and Multinational Trials on Human Subjects	
Questions and answers	

Break (EET, UTC/GMT+3h: 13.25 – 13.30; USA EDT, UTC/GMT-4h: 06.25-06.30)

Section II – Humanity, Scientific Research and Academic Ethics (EET, UTC/GMT+3h: 13.30 – 15.30; USA EDT, UTC/GMT-4h: 06.30-08.30)

Chair: Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru. ‘Timotheus’ Brethren Theological Institute – Romania

Discussants: Serban Turcus. “Babes-Bolyai” University – Romania

Paul Brusanowski. “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu – Romania

Stelian Manolache. “Ovidius” University – Romania

Marian Simion. Harvard Divinity School & The Institute for Peace Studies in Eastern Christianity – United States of America

Nelu Burcea. United Nations Liaison for IRLA and SDA – United States of America

Ethical Conditioning over the Last Decade History between Challenges of Nationalism and those of Globalization	Serban Turcus. “Babes-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca– Romania & Veronica Turcus. Romanian Academy Cluj-Napoca / “George Baritiu” History Institute – Romania
Scientific Research on the Human Rights perspectives of Freedom of Thoughts and Academic Ethics	Nelu Burcea. United Nations Liaison for IRLA and SDA – United States of America
Research Methodology in Church History	Paul Brusanowski. “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu – Romania
Ethical and Moral in Setting Thresholds Regarding the Level of Similarities in Undergraduate and Graduate Theses	Dumitru Vanca. “1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia – Romania
The Importance of Moral Virtues for Academic Research	Corneliu Simuț. Emanuel University of Oradea & Aurel Vlaicu University of Arad –

	<i>Romania</i>
The Relationship between Academic Ethics and the Author's Morality	Stelian Manolache. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Divine Principles of the Decalogue and Plagiarism	Ieremia Rusu. <i>"Timotheus' Brethren Theological Institute of Bucharest – Romania</i>
Nationalism by Proxy	Adela Burcea. <i>Paul Valery University – France</i>
Ethical Principles in Current Philological Research	Nina Corcinschi. <i>The "Bogdan Petriceicu Haşdeu" Institute of Romanian Philology of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Research – Republic of Moldova</i>
Ethical Considerations on Psychological Research	Maria Belea. <i>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca/North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania</i>
The Freedom of Access to Knowledge as a Moral Value	Osman Murat Deniz. <i>Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi – Turkey</i>
Etical Research on the Religious Integration of Interfaith Families as the Misionary Work of the Church	Tudor-Cosmin Ciocan. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Harmonization of Theological Dissensions through an Ethic of Academic Contingency	Remus Soare. <i>SDA Adventist Church, Spanish Union – Spain</i>
New Approaches regarding Scientific Research and Academic Ethics in the Education Science	Mihai Covaci. <i>Hyperion University – Romania & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria</i>
Religion as a Subject in Primary Education. Conflict or Synergy between Social Norms and Religious Perceptions?	Zorica Aurica Triff. <i>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania</i>
Freedom of Religion or Belief in the Context of Didactics of Embryology and Genetics in Medical Education	Dorin-Gheorghe Triff. <i>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania</i>

Current Challenges in Research Ethics within the University Environment	Iulian Militaru. <i>Romanian-American University – Romania</i>
Ethics of Scientific Research in Specific Situations of Social Assistance	Nechita Marius. <i>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania</i>
Ethics and the Scientific Research of the Bible	Corneliu Constantineanu. <i>“Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad – Romania</i>
Guiding Principles in the Ethical Code of Science	Arthur Wagner. <i>Independent Scholar – Germany</i>
Analysis of the Cognition-Metacognition-Learning Relationship. Research on the Development of Metacognitive Behavior	Monica Maier. <i>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania</i>
Scientific Research and its Humanist Spirit	Cătălina Mititelu. <i>“Ovidius” University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Theological Discourse and the Claim that God Speaks: Ethical Implications of Biblical Interpretive Methods	Marcel Măcelaru. <i>“Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad – Romania</i>
The mission of the Church reflected in Ethics and Academic Research at the Beginning of the third Millennium	Gheorghe Istodor. <i>“Ovidius” University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Ethics of Online Academic Education and Research	Daniel Fodorean. <i>Baptist Theological Institute of Bucharest – Romania</i>
Research regarding History of the Sabbatarians from Transylvania (16th-20th centuries)	Ioan Gheorghe Rotaru. <i>“Timotheus’ Brethren Theological Institute of Bucharest & “Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad – Romania</i>

Police Ethics and Deontology as a Study Discipline for the "Local Police" Bachelors Degree Program	Gheorghe Buzescu. <i>"Ovidius" University of Constanta – Romania</i>
Questions and answers	

Conclusions and Closing Speeches (EET, UTC/GMT+3h: 15.30 – 16.00; USA EDT, UTC/GMT-4h: 08.30-09.00)

Tamara Abigail Peicu. *University of Vienna – Austria*

Gheorghe Radu. *Athenaeum University – Romania*

Otilia Manta. *Romanian Academy / "Victor Slavescu" Center for Financial and Monetary Research, "Athenaeum" University of Bucharest – Romania & School of International University Studies / Istituto di Ricerca di Dr. Arioli S.a.s. – Italy & Vice-President of the European Union Experts (EUExperts) – Belgium*